

**Synthesis of 1,2,4-Triazino[3,4-*d*]-
[1,3,4]oxadiazine**

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CONDENSED 1,2,4-triazines have been established as potent biologically active agents¹. Various methods² have been reported for the synthesis of condensed 1,2,4-triazines. The present paper deals with the synthesis of 1,2,4-triazino[3,4-*d*]-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazin-3-one from 2-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazin-5-one. In view of the potential monooxidase enzyme activity of 2-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazin-5-one, we thought of incorporating triazine system to this oxadiazine nucleus

and to study the chemical and biological properties of the resulting systems.

The oxadiazinone (2), prepared from salicylhydrazide (1) following a reported method³, was reacted with ethyl bromoacetate and sodium hydroxide in acetone to afford the corresponding ethoxy-carbonylmethyl derivative (3; R=OEt), identified by spectral data. On treatment of 3 (R=OEt) with hydrazine hydrate, the open-chain acid hydrazide (3; R=NHNH₂) was obtained instead of the expected triazine (5). This may be attributed to low electrophilicity of the carbonyl group. To increase the electrophilicity, 3 (R=OEt) was converted to its thio analogue (4) using phosphorus pentasulphide.

The thione (4) was further refluxed with equimolar quantity of ethanolic hydrazine hydrate to give the cyclised product 5 (R¹=H), identified by elemental analysis and ir spectra. Similarly, the triazinone 5 (R¹=Ph) was obtained from 4 using phenylhydrazine (Scheme 1). The structure of the triazinone 5 (R¹=H) was further confirmed by its conversion (Ac₂O/Py) to the corresponding acetate. The *O*-acetyl structure (6) was preferred to the *N*-acetyl structure since such acetylation of 2 has earlier been reported³ to give *O*-acetyl derivative and since this structure follows from the Katritzky's generalisation⁴ on the enolisation of amides.

Scheme 1

The triazinones 5 (R¹=H and Ph) underwent hydrolysis in refluxing acidic condition giving the acid derivative 3 (R=OH). The acid was identified by its esterification to the ester (3; R=OEt), identified by m.p. and superimposable ir spectra. Such type of ring cleavage by acid has been reported earlier³,

when salicylic acid was obtained from the acid hydrolysis of 1,3,4-oxadiazinone (2).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded in KBr and pmr spectra (90 MHz) in CDCl₃/TMS. 5,6-Dihydro-2-*o*-hydroxyphenyl-4*H*-1,3,4-oxadiazin-5-one was prepared by the method described earlier³.

Ethyl 5,6-dihydro-2-o-hydroxyphenyl-4H-1,3,4-oxadiazin-5-one-4-acetate (3; R=OEt): To a suspension of 2 (1.92 g, 0.01 mol) in acetone (40 ml), was added 4% sodium hydroxide solution (12 ml) with stirring, when the solid first dissolved and later the sodium salt precipitated. To it was added ethyl bromoacetate (1.84 g, 0.011 mol) and the mixture was stirred for 3 h at room temperature, then excess acetone removed and cooled to room temperature. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol, (1.8 g, 65%), m.p. 134° (Found: C, 56.88; H, 4.73; N, 9.86. C₁₃H₁₄O₅N₂ requires: C, 56.11; H, 5.03; N, 10.07%); ν_{\max} 3 150 (phenolic OH), 1 730 (ester C=O), 1 680 (C=O) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 1.3 (3H, t, *J* 8 Hz, CH₃), 4.25 (2H, q, *J* 8 Hz, CH₂), 4.5 (2H, s, N-CH₂COOEt), 4.8 (2H, s, CH₂ cyclic), 7.0–7.8 (4H, m, ArH) and 10.1 (1H, s, OH).

5,6-Dihydro-2-o-hydroxyphenyl-4H-1,3,4-oxadiazin-5-one-4-acetic acid hydrazide (3; R=NHNH₂): A solution of hydrazine hydrate (0.6 ml, 0.013 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) was added with stirring to a suspension of 3 (2.78 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) and refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight and the resulting crystalline material was filtered, (2.11 g, 80%), m.p. >280°; ν_{\max} 3 150 (Ph-OH), 3 310–3 320 (NH-NH₂), 1 700 (CONH), 1 680 (C=O) and 1 630 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

Ethyl 5,6-dihydro-2-o-hydroxyphenyl-4H-1,3,4-oxadiazin-5-thione-4-acetate (4): A mixture of the oxo-ester 3 (5.56 g, 0.02 mol) and P₂S₅ (4.88 g, 0.022 mol) was refluxed in dry dioxane (100 ml) for ~4 h. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the filtrate concentrated to one-fourth of its volume under reduced pressure. The concentrate was then poured onto crushed ice and allowed to stand overnight. The resulting yellow crystalline solid was crystallised from ethanol (4.1 g, 69.7%), m.p. 111° (Found: C, 53.2; H, 4.85, N, 9.40; S, 10.71. C₁₃H₁₄O₄N₂S requires: C, 53.06; H, 4.76; N, 9.52; S, 10.88%); ν_{\max} 3 080 (Ph-OH), 1 720 (C=O), 1 610 (C=N) and 1 210 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ 1.3 (3H, t, *J* 8 Hz, CH₃), 4.4 (2H, q, *J* 8 Hz, ester CH₂), 4.65 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 5.0 (2H, s, ring CH₂), 7.5–8.0 (4H, m, ArH) and 10.3 (1H, s, OH).

(2H)-3-Oxo-7-o-hydroxyphenyl-1,2,4-triazino[3,4-d][1,3,4]oxadiazine (5; R¹=H): To a hot solution of the thio ester 4 (2.94 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was added hydrazine hydrate (0.55 ml, 0.012 mol) and the mixture refluxed for 0.5 h. The resulting yellow solid after hot filtration was washed with hot ethanol

and crystallised from dioxane, (2.35 g, 95.5%), m.p. $>250^\circ$ (Found: C, 54.0; H, 3.85; N, 22.39. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3N_4$ requires: C, 53.66; H, 4.06; N, 22.76%); ν_{\max} 3 200 (Ph-OH), 3 050 (NH), 1 650 (C=O), 1 620 (PhC=N) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=N).

3-Oxo-2-phenyl-7-o-hydroxyphenyl-1,2,4-triazino-[3,4-d][1,3,4]oxadiazine (5; R¹=Ph): To hot solution of the thio ester 4 (2.94 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml), was added phenyl hydrazine (1.29 g, 0.012 mol) and the mixture refluxed for 2 h. The solution was concentrated to half of its volume and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The resulting pale yellow solid was recrystallised from ethanol, (2.5 g, 77.6%), m.p. 204° (Found: C, 63.60; H, 4.59; N, 17.01. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3N_4$ requires: C, 63.35; H, 4.35; N, 17.39%); ν_{\max} 3 500br (OH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 655 (C=N) and 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=N of triazine ring); δ 4.75 (2H, s, CH₂ of triazine ring), 5.2 (2H, s, CH₂ of oxadiazine ring), 7.1–7.4 (4H, m, ArH), 7.5–8.0 (5H, m, ArH) and 10.7 (1H, s, OH).

Acetylation of the triazine (5; R¹=H): The triazine (5, R¹=H; 1 g) was refluxed in acetic anhydride (10 ml) containing a few drops of pyridine for ~6 h. It was then cooled to room temperature and the resulting solid was crystallised from glacial acetic acid to yield 6 (0.95 g, 70.9%), m.p. $>250^\circ$; ν_{\max} 1 755 (C=O of acetyl), 1 680, 1 650 and 1 615 cm^{-1} (C=N).

5,6-Dihydro-2-o-hydroxyphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazin-5-one-(2H)-4-acetic acid (3; R=OH): The triazine (5, R¹=H, Ph; 1 g) was refluxed in dioxane (20 ml) containing dilute HCl (1 ml) for ~1 h. The solution was then concentrated and poured over cold water. The resulting white solid was recrystallised from ethanol: m.p. 228° , (0.8 g, 78.7%) from 5 (R¹=H) and (0.5 g, 64.4%) from 5 (R¹=Ph); ν_{\max} 3 100–3 200br (both OH), 1 740 (C=O of acid), 1 655 (C=O) and 1 630 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Esterification of the acid 3 (R=OH). Formation of 3 (R=OEt): The acid (3, R=OH; 2.50 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (25 ml) with a few drops of concentrated H₂SO₄ for ~4 h. The mixture was then concentrated to half of the volume and cooled to room temperature. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol to give 3 (R=OEt), (1.95 g, 70.1%), m.p. 134° .

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